

Development, design & construction of baby diapers, and sanitary napkins for hygienic aspects from the renewable fiber

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KEY WORDS

Banana fiber
Biodegradable
Sanitary napkins
Diapers
Natural absorbent fiber
Disposal
Sustainable
Eco-friendly

ABSTRACT

Everyone is focused on eliminating environmental issues and nature degradation in order to create an eco-friendly environment. In addition, maintaining good health and hygiene is crucial for humans. The textile sector is the source of the greatest pollution, which is a significant issue for the production and disposal of diapers and sanitary products. Only a small portion of women in Bangladesh use sanitary napkins. The fundamental explanation for such a low number has to do with people's ability to pay. Banana fiber and cotton, which are readily available, biodegradable, and inexpensive materials, were used in the current investigation. Utilizing natural materials had the added benefit of being more porous and retaining fluid for longer. The findings showed that the napkins are environmentally beneficial. The companies manufacture non-biodegradable and harmful to women's and infants' health napkins and diapers. Every woman's health and lifestyle should be improved by the use of sanitary napkins in addition to comfort and safety. In order to overcome these problems, here we are proposing sustainable sanitary napkins by choosing alternative Banana fiber for production. In the present study, an attempt has been made to produce sanitary napkins from banana fiber, a natural absorbent fiber. These fibers have some important properties like antioxidants, biodegradable, UV protection, and weather protection. It has no negative effect on the environment and it is considered an eco-friendly fiber.

1 Introduction

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in finding sustainable alternatives to traditional baby diapers and sanitary napkins, driven by increased global consciousness towards environmental preservation. The production, usage, and disposal of these personal hygiene products often rely on synthetic materials derived from non-renewable resources, contributing to environmental pollution and resource depletion. Consequently, researchers and manufacturers have turned their attention towards renewable and eco-friendly materials, such as banana fiber, to address these concerns.

Also a growing global concern regarding the environmental impact of conventional baby diapers and sanitary napkins, as well as the accessibility and affordability of these products, particularly in developing countries like Bangladesh. Traditional manufacturing processes and materials used in these products contribute to high manufacturing costs, making them inaccessible to a significant portion of the population (CHANANA, 2016). Moreover, the disposal of non-biodegradable diapers and napkins further exacerbates environmental pollution. Therefore, it is imperative to explore sustainable and cost-effective alternatives to address both hygienic and affordability aspects. This thesis aims to investigate the potential of banana fiber-based nonwoven sheets as a sustainable solution for reducing manufacturing costs and producing low-cost sanitary napkins in Bangladesh.

The high manufacturing costs associated with conventional baby diapers and sanitary napkins primarily stem from the extensive use of synthetic materials and energy-intensive processes. This research focuses on utilizing banana fiber as a raw material to develop a cost-effective alternative that can significantly reduce manufacturing expenses. Banana fiber, abundantly available as a byproduct of banana cultivation in Bangladesh, offers a locally sourced and sustainable material option (Sareen, 2021). Incorporating banana fiber into the production process can lead to a substantial reduction in costs, making baby diapers and sanitary napkins more affordable and accessible to a wider segment of the population.

To achieve this aim, the research will investigate various aspects such as sourcing banana fiber, optimizing the manufacturing process, and evaluating the cost-effectiveness of incorporating banana fiber into the production of baby diapers and sanitary napkins. The goal is to identify practical and efficient methods that can reduce manufacturing costs without compromising the hygiene and quality standards of these products.

In addition to cost reduction, this research emphasizes the importance of sustainability in the production of baby diapers and sanitary napkins. By utilizing banana fiber, a renewable and biodegradable material, the environmental impact associated with non-biodegradable products can be mitigated. Banana fiber exhibits desirable properties such as high tensile strength, absorbency, and breathability, which are crucial for maintaining hygiene and preventing skin irritations.

The research will explore methods for efficiently processing banana fiber into suitable forms for baby diapers and sanitary napkins. It will also evaluate the performance of banana fiber-based products in terms of absorbency, breathability, comfort, and overall user satisfaction. Additionally, the environmental impact of utilizing banana fiber will be assessed, considering factors such as the reduction in waste generation and the potential for biodegradation.

By reducing manufacturing costs and promoting sustainable practices, this research aims to make significant progress towards providing affordable and environmentally friendly options for baby diapers and sanitary napkins in Bangladesh. The findings of this study will contribute to improving the accessibility of these essential hygiene products while simultaneously addressing the environmental challenges associated with their production and disposal.

2 Literature Reviews

2.1 Historical background

Egyptian women used tampons with softened papyrus. Pads and tampons in Rome are composed of soft woolen cloth. Other materials used to make menstrual flow containment devices across the world include paper, moss, wool, animal skins, and grass (Lopamudra Ganguly, Lakshminarayan Satpat, Sreeparna Nath, 2022). In 1896, a commercial sanitary pad was made by Johnson and Johnson Company as “Lister’s Towels (Nayak, 2017). Many American women used handmade pads in the early twentieth century. In the early 20th century, American women utilised homemade pads. Their undergarments or custom-made muslin belts were fastened with these fabrics or rags. In order to prevent stains on clothing without absorbing blood flow, sanitary aprons and bloomers were also provided (Lopamudra Ganguly, Lakshminarayan Satpat, Sreeparna Nath, 2022; Lopamudra Ganguly, Lakshminarayan Satpat, Sreeparna Nath, 2022).

The first sanitary pads with short adhesive strips, called tiny pads, were introduced by Stayfree in 1969 (Period, 2021). Modern Era and Menstrual Products are reusable cloth pads, commercial sanitary pads, Tampons, Reusable tampons, menstrual cups, Bamboo fiber pads, Banana fiber pads, Water hyacinth pads (Rajanbir Kaur, Kanwaljit Kaur, and Rajindar Kaur, 2018).

Before disposable diapers were developed, all newborns in North America used cloth diapers. The diaper delivery business was created during World War II to provide working moms with new, clean diapers. Pampers, a product of Proctor & Gamble, was the first disposable diaper. With the Huggies brand, Kimberly Clark went on to become the second-largest maker of disposable diapers. The marketing budgets for disposable diapers were massive, and they were convenient and absorbent (Krafchik, 2016).

These days, cheap and clean pads for rural ladies produced from the banana tree fiber were sold under trademark “Saathi” in India (Saathi, 2015). They are environmentally friendly and break down a year after usage. The production of bananas produces extra material, which is known as banana fibers. Therefore, these fibers may be

purchased for the current sanitary pad business at no additional expense. The banana plant yields both delicious natural goods and useful fiber. One of the strongest natural fibers now accessible is banana fiber. Banana fiber shares a physical structure with ramie fiber. It is a natural fiber known as a cellulosic structure made of cellulose, hemicelluloses, lignin, etc. (Ankita Shroff, Anjali Karolia, Jayendra narottamdas Shah, 2015)

The moisture absorbency of this fiber is 10% - 11.5%. This fiber has strong moisture absorption quality as it absorbs and releases moisture very fast (Shanmuga Shri, Safrin Shynie, Baranitharan, 2022). It qualifies as eco-friendly fiber since it is biodegradable and has no adverse environmental effects (Neenu Poonia, Nisha Arya, and Pooja, 2020). Banana fibers are now being used more often in clothing and home furnishings as sustainable textile goods become more prevalent (Shanmuga Shri M, Safrin Shynie A, and Baranitharan K, 2022).

Production of Sanitary Napkins is by Multinational firms using expensive machineries. Efforts have been made to develop and market simple and low cost machines which can be used in rural setup. Napkins made using these locally accessible equipment are 25–30% less expensive than the cheapest category napkins already on the market. The major cost is of the raw material used for absorption. To improve productivity and lower costs for napkins, there is considerable room to experiment with alternative materials. Most MNCs now engaged in the production of sanitary napkins use pine wood pulp that is imported from several foreign nations. This wood pulp is costly and none of the organization in Bangladesh produces it. Some small village level units use waste shoddy cotton which is unhygienic. Bagasse pulp, water hyacinth pulp, banana stem pulp, bamboo pulp, and cotton knit wear waste pulp were some of the alternatives to wood pulp that were discovered in an initial investigation of potential alternatives in India. All these are indigenous materials and their availability is in abundance across the country (CHANANA, 2016).

2.2 Theory Relevant Research

One theoretical model that could be relevant in this context is the construction. Sanitary pad consists of three main layers and these are- the top sheet, absorbent core and barrier sheet (Barman A, Katkar PM and Asagekar SD, 2017) (Siddiqe, 2019). As a result of its higher liquid retention capabilities, non-irritating nature, and skin friendliness, organic cotton is one of the most frequently recommended raw materials for sanitary napkins. It is supple and permeable, providing comfort and dryness. However, diapers also have a number of layers. Adult diapers have a top sheet, distribution layer, absorbent core, back sheet, cuff system, and elastic leg gatherers, identical to baby diapers. The inner layer of an adult diaper should quickly transmit fluids to the layer below it while it is facing the skin. High levels of softness are required for the layer that directly contacts the skin. The liquid is blocked and absorbed by the absorbent core layer, which is made up of a combination of cellulose flakes and highly absorbent polymer. Against the garment, the upper layer creates a barrier that keeps moisture out. As a result, it often comprises of a permeable nonwoven polyethylene composite that is

also kind to skin or a polyethylene film (Mankodi Hireni, Dalsania Krishna, 2019).

2.3 Current Empirical Literature

There is a dearth of material that focuses explicitly on the use of banana fiber in hygiene products like sanitary pads and diapers. However, several researches have looked at the usage of banana fiber in regular sanitary pads. Banana fiber is manually removed from the pseudo-stem of the plant. The fibers are extracted, broken up into little pieces, and then cooked for an hour in 150 mL of distilled water with 5 grams of sodium hydroxide or MgHO. After that, the liquid is allowed to cool for about an hour and a half to create a thin coating. The organic cotton was stretched out on the thin banana sheet and covered with the muslin cloth. The corner of the canvas was softened after encasing the entire set of sheets in it (Rahul Vinod Nai, and Rachana RK Nair, 2021) (Antoinette Consolascion R. Pinera, Christina Jayne Bayani, 2020).

Another study titled “Development of Eco-Friendly Sanitary Napkins using *Sansevieria trifasciata* Fibres coated with *Rosa damascena* Extracts” highlights the issue of non biodegradability of commercial sanitary pads and importance of sanitary napkin absorbent core made from *Sansevieria trifasciata* plant fibres which is environmentally friendly and biodegradable. Overall the study suggest that *Sansevieria trifasciata* plant fibres can be used as absorbent core which is emitted the Super Absorbent Polymer which is known to cause skin irritation and toxic shock syndrome and cancer (Mekala, 2021). And also antimicrobial finish on *Sansevieria trifasciata* plant fibers using neem extraction.

Another study by Rahul Vinod Nair and Rachana RK Nair explore the banana fiber used in sanitary pad. The researchers found that the application of banana fiber, converted it into pulp and thin film sheet.

Furthermore, a study titled “NOVEL TYPE OF ADULT DIAPER FROM NATURAL FIBERS” In this work novel concept of adult diaper using natural fibers has been introduced. Natural banana fiber and hemp fiber has been used to make the core of the adult diaper eliminating the super absorbent polymers making the product more biodegradable. The researchers diaper core using banana and hemp fiber. The banana and hemp fibers core has been prepared by formation of web on card (Mankodi Hireni, Dalsania Krishna, 2019).

Bhawana Chanana also concentrated on the significance of low-cost sanitary napkins in developing nations and attempted to introduce some alternative materials for sanitary napkins in order to make them accessible to women in the Lower Income Group. It is crucial to develop a low-cost technology for the production of these products.

In conclusion, previous studies have explored the use of banana fiber in menstrual hygiene and the potentiality lower cost menstrual hygiene product for developing countries. Our study aims to produce more efficient and lower cost Menstrual Products from banana fiber upon these methodologies.

3 Materials and Methodology

3.1 Materials

The diaper core has been prepared using banana fiber (Figure-1). The raw banana fiber has been collected from a local buyer of Tangail and dried in the shade for 5 days. All the chemicals (Sodium hydroxide, Hydrogen peroxide, Peroxide killer, wetting agent, sequestering agent, Sulphuric acid) used in this work were reagent grade. In the value creation chain from the fiber to the nonwoven fabric, carding is a crucial process step for efficient production. The card web is created during the carding process, which gently separates and then recombines fibers to create a homogenous fiber mat. During the carding process, every component of the raw material is fully combined, and any foreign material is exposed and filtered out (Figure-2). Only if all of the fibers employed contribute to producing the physical qualities of the card web can the raw material input be kept to a minimum. For the cost-effective production of nonwovens, all fibers must be mixed and distributed in the card web uniformly.

Figure-1

Figure-2

3.2 Experimental Setup

To increase absorbency and make the fiber more absorbent need to remove fat, lignin, and waxy material. In this method, there use a 5gm/200ml NaOH solution with 1ml sodium carbonate, 1ml wetting agent, and 1ml sequestering agent. Then add 10gm banana fibers and treat it at 95°C temperature for 60 minutes. Then wash and dry it properly.

Before

After

Figure-3: Before & After Scouring Process.

To remove the natural color from fiber, a common step is bleaching. There use 3ml hydrogen peroxide and stabilizer for each 5gm fiber. As auxiliaries 0.5ml wetting agent and sequestering

agent and 1:20 ratio water is needed to treat the fiber. The treated temperature is 95°C with a running time of 60 minutes.

Figure-4: Before & After Bleaching Process.

To remove lignin from banana fiber, need to treat it with a mild acid. In this experiment, there used a very mild concentration of Sulphuric acid. Approximately, 15ml Sulphuric acid of 50% concentration. Then mixed it with 100ml water. Each 5gm sample is treated with this solution at 35°C with a running time of 60 minutes.

Figure-5: Before & After Acid Treat.

3.3 Final Product Making Procedure:

At First, spread the fiber and then spray a little amount of water. Then heat press on the sample by using a hand iron. For this water spray and heat press, fibers being adhere to each other. Keep the sample rest for 1-2 hours. Then cut the fiber sheet according to the sanitary napkin and diaper shape. Place the cutting piece on a polyethylene back sheet. Spread a little amount of sodium polyacrylate powder (super absorbent gel). Place a white bleached cotton sheet. Then roll the whole sample with a cotton non-woven top sheet (18GSM). The baby Diaper making process is the same but there attaches elastic with the leg opening side and waist for special facilities of wearing. Use adhesive (Hot melt glue) to attach every part of the diaper.

Figure-6: Final Products.

4 Design Model of Sanitary Napkin & Baby Diaper:

The design of sanitary napkins consists of three parts: Top sheet, Core, and Bottom sheet as shown in figure-7. The top sheet consists of a layer of cotton nonwoven followed by layers of web in the core and lastly, the bottom sheet which consists of a non-permeable sheet sandwiched between two layers of nonwoven. The diaper design model is similar to the sanitary napkin design model but their use of sodium polyacrylate as an absorbent gel in between banana core fiber and a nonpermeable bottom sheet (Figure-8).

Figure-7: Design Model of Sanitary Napkin.

Figure-8: Design model of baby diaper

5 Experimental Results & Discussion:

5.1 Absorbency test: ISO 5405-1980

This method determines the total absorption capacity of the material. According to the test standard ISO 5405-1980, a sample is laid on a flat level and transparent surface, so that the underside of the pad can be observed. Fluid is to be dripped, at the rate of 15ml per minute, so that 30 ml of the fluid maintained at a temperature of 27^oC is poured onto the of fluid, and the standard weight of 1 kg is put above the sample for a minute on the portion where the fluid is absorbed center of the sanitary pad from a height of approx. 1 to 2 mm. After the napkin has absorbed the full amount. After that, the back and sides of the pad are observed for fluid flowing up. The reading is recorded.

5.2 Sanitary napkin absorbency test result:

Weight of Sanitary napkin = 14.62 gm

Water absorb = 27.57 ml

Absorbency capacity= $27.57/14.62 = 1.886$ g/g

5.3 Diaper absorbency test result:

Weight of Diaper= 23.59 gm

Water absorb = 226.41 ml

Absorbency capacity= $226.41/23.59 = 9.58$ g/g

5.4 Discussion

For sanitary napkins,

From the result of the overall performance of the sample, we can see our 12.54-gram product absorbs 23.65 ml of liquid. On the other hand, a normal sanitary napkin absorbs 20 ml of liquid. So, we can say that our product is capable of use.

For Diaper,

From the result of the overall performance of the sample, we can see our 24.81-gram product absorbs 226.41 ml of liquid. On the other hand, a normal diaper absorbs 160 - 170 ml of liquid. Zero to 4-month-old baby daily excretes 180 - 190ml liquid. So, we can say that our product is capable of use.

6 Conclusion:

This study has the purpose to make sanitary napkins, and baby diapers using natural fibers with effective properties. As we can see that they use renewable fiber and develop such materials which can replace synthetic materials. As a result, there is an increase in demand for commercial use of natural fiber-based products. Natural fibers are sustainable materials that are easily available in nature and have advantages like low-cost, lightweight, renewability, biodegradability, and high specific properties. The sustainability of natural fiber-based composite materials has led to their applications in various manufacturing sectors. Recently, natural resources are gaining attention in solving the problems faced by people around the world. This study proved that the replacement of non-degradable material with biodegradable material for developing hygienic feminine products is eco-friendly and cost-effective. Use of natural material in napkins will be cost-effective and it can be affordable by the lower income people. Using this technology, we can find a suitable solution to make the world better for future generations.

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